

Ugly Architecture reaches 50,000 members and looks for a partner institution

(announcement)

0. Information about this document

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Abstract: The Facebook group *Ugly Architecture* has reached 50,000 members. Its goal from the beginning was to promote post-war Czech, especially socialist modern architecture, by regularly showing this architecture and discussing it. At the same time, over the years of its existence, it has discovered many objects, some of which are not even in the official databases of experts. Therefore, we are seeking a strategic partner among professional foreign institutions, such as universities or museums, with whom we can collaborate to create this database. We are also considering the problems caused by the increase in the number of members and the fatigue of older members, and we are exploring win-win models through cooperation with students of architecture and related subjects.

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1. About the group

1.1. Basics and history

Ugly Architecture is an English translation of a czech public Facebook group called *Ošklivá architektura*¹, which was founded in February 2018 by Jan Lochman, to promote an interest in socialist modernist architecture in the Czech Republic as a reaction of the announced demolition of Transgas complex. Since then the group got a broader scope to focus on everything endangered from the second half of the 20th century. It welcomes members to look for, photograph, and present buildings constructed between 1945 and 2000 in the Czech Republic or other parts of the world, as well as occasionally art and design in architecture. The discussion about the history and qualities of such buildings is also welcome.

1.2. Participants

As of October 2025, the group has more than 51,000 members and 12,000 visitors. The majority of members fall within the 25–45 age range. The ratio of men and women is almost 1:1. Followers and contributors include both experts, such as conservationists and architects,² as well as students in these fields and the general public. Our goal is to create an environment without barriers that allows everyone to consume content and contribute their own contributions. That is why the term "ugly architecture" was used, as we believed it reflected the predominant perception of architecture from the second half of the 20th century. In other words, the goal was not to create a club of enthusiasts for this architecture (naming it, for example, Socmodern Architecture), but to provide an open platform for dialogue between proponents and opponents of styles such as socialist realism or socialist modernism. Group members are mainly located in cities, which respects the demographic distribution of the Czech people.

1.3. Content

Since its foundation, the group has collected thousands of locations and retrieved and disseminated meta-information of a specific kind, such as identifying the authors of specific buildings or design patterns, and provided it to Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons, and other platforms. However, the exact numbers are hard to tell as Facebook does not provide us with statistics. On the other hand, we know the number of buildings for big cities and some small towns, as we possess some off-site databases.³⁴

2. Future goals

Since we have collected a lot of valuable information, and at the same time, Facebook is not a suitable platform for storing or retrieving previously recorded information, we would like to create

1 Link to the group: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/OsklivaArchitektura>

2 Posts from experts are infrequent, so they are more likely to consume group content.

3 An example is our online simple database of buildings for Prague: <https://praha.osklivaarchitektura.cz/>

4 Another example is of endangered buildings: <https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?mid=1rtyXEredTvkXtw8fLV3RHUcSIQK4hs&usp=sharing>

an external, freely accessible database to store this information. The other goal is to enhance our users' knowledge, particularly in the area of social modernist architecture. For both purposes, we are looking for a strategic partner, like a university, which would help us to achieve our goals and win an interesting dataset, with the potential to provide their students with a learning experience. *If any organisation is interested in such cooperation, please feel free to contact the project founder, Mr. Lochman, via email at janlochman at gmail.com.*

2.1. Towards the architecture database

We have found that when searching for a keyword, such as a town name, in a Facebook group, not all available results are displayed.⁵ Therefore, people who want to compile a list of sites to read about or visit may not receive all available information. This situation makes our desire for a database more urgent. Repeated searches for the exact locations and issues with data filtering led other group members to believe that a database on a more robust platform could solve the problem.

We have already been experimenting with two models for creating a database: Wikibase,⁶ and Google Sheets combined with a map on the website. The first option is a more effective way of entering and storing information, with its features of linked knowledge and a robust query service; however, users would need to learn how to contribute and curate the information. Wikibase Cloud is an insecure platform for long-term storage; therefore, this solution would also require a donation of a server and bandwidth from the partner institution. Mr. Lochman could provide his expertise in setting up the environment and modeling information.⁷ The second option, storing data in tabs, might be easier for contributors. However, it's confusing, prone to errors due to cell mismatches, and as a result, has fewer filtering and information search options for end users.

Data for this database can come from our existing external databases and from users who have already agreed to provide their data. Some users are even willing to learn the new environment and contribute directly to it. Data from the Facebook group may serve as references. Since the group includes members from across the country (Fig. 1), we can occasionally ask individuals to document objects in their local area.

Figure 1. Proportional circle map showing the number of members in municipalities. Just communities of more than 100 members are included

⁵ For example, Mr. Lochman has created a database for the town of Chlumec nad Cidlinou in Google Sheets. Then he photographed it and created posts for the Facebook group. After that, he stored links to these posts. After some time, if someone is looking for that location using “Chlumec” or “Cidlinou” keywords, they are not offered all the posts for that location.

⁶ The link to test Wikibase: <https://web.archive.org/web/20251004172327/https://uglyarchitecture.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Special:AllPages?from=&to=&namespace=120>

⁷ During the Wikibase testing, Mr. Lochman worked on a simple, strict model that does not contain as many nuances as, for example, Wikidata, but can be simpler for both users entering information and those seeking information. An example of such modeling is at this link:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20251004172839/https://uglyarchitecture.wikibase.cloud/w/index.php?title=User:Juandev/Modelov%C3%A1n%C3%AD&oldid=626%2A>

To improve the database Mr. Lochman can provide data like authors, years of creation etc. from his extensive collection of books on the topic, which are from 60 % digitized, so the information retrieval might be much faster.

2.2 Improving consumer knowledge

The group's content consumption is not limited to group members, but also includes other people on the internet, as evidenced by the fact that fifty thousand people displayed the group's content in September 2025.

There are multiple ways to improve the quality of the content. One approach is to mix it with more advanced posts created by professionals or semi-professionals – students of architectural history. This would depend on whether we could find such a partner.

3. Conclusions

The original goal of the project, to establish a platform where people would be interested in post-war architecture themselves, was fulfilled. After the initial years, when only the founder added posts and motivated people to discuss, other interested parties appeared who actively search for interesting buildings, information about them, and share their findings with others. They take over the administration of the group and start organizing offline activities.

It can either be left as it is or utilized to rework the information obtained into a new medium that will enable long-term preservation and advanced filtering options for both scientific and educational purposes. Already today, users in the group are searching for buildings that they would like to visit or about which they are processing a report.

The issue of continuous growth is also important. The increasing number of contributions can cause a negative influx of posts into the group. Likewise, some old users are already complaining that they would like to see only new buildings or consume more professional content. The question is, what approach should we choose? To leave the group to its fate, to devise a system to keep this continuous growth stable, or to prohibit growth altogether?

One solution could be an external database where it can be recorded whether a given building was presented in the group. Additional information can be searched for and then presented in the form of more professional articles, again in the group. It is possible to contact an external educational institution whose students would provide such more professional contributions (thanks to the efficient translators, language is no longer such a problem) and, thanks to studying our materials, obtain interesting information on the field of architectural history and, at the same time, become familiar with the methods of promoting architecture.

In essence, many things can be done, but some institutional support is needed for them. That is why we are seeking external partners from universities, museums, and possibly archives or high schools, to whom we would offer our data and knowledge, and in return, obtain some institutional or material support.